

Distribution of Single Particle Energy and the Maxwell-Boltzmann Gas Part II

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In Part I, we tried to argue that the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution is associated with an energy, and not momentum, distribution. We suggested that the phase space associated with momentum is used to calculate allowable momentum states, but not yield the probability distribution.

In (1), a gas of $n-1$ -dimensional momentum particles is considered by considering the equation: $\sum_{i=1, n-1} p(i)p(i) = RR$ where $E=RR/2m$ and $p(i)$ is the single component of momentum of the i th particle. If the n th particle has energy e , then $\sum_{i=1, n-1} p(i)p(i) = RR - p(n)p(n)$ where $p(n)p(n)=e/2m$. (1) suggests that the probability $P(e)$ is proportional to the surface area of an $n-1$ sphere, which in turn is proportional to $\sqrt{E-e}$ power $(n-1)/2$.

In (2), we suggested that one use nested energy to find the probability. For $n=4$ particles, the fourth particle has energy e , and the first particle has whatever energy is left over after particles 2 and 3 have been assigned energy. Thus, probability is proportional to: $\int_0^{E-e} de_2 \int_0^{E-e-e_2} de_3$. We found that in general $P(e)$ is proportional to $(E-e)$ power $(n-2)$.

For high n , the approach of (1) yields $P(e)$ proportional to $(E-e)$ power $(n/2)$ while the approach of (2) yields $P(e)$ proportional to $(E-e)$ power (n) .

Here we consider the $n=2$ case to show why there is a difference and argue in favour of the approach of (2). The key difference, we argue, is that for the $n=2$ case, (1) is equivalent to dividing a line in equal dp pieces from 0 to $\sqrt{E} C$, where C is a constant. Given a p , one immediately knows the value of p_2 (the second particle) from $e_1 + e_2 = E$. The probability is then proportional to the length of the line, namely $\sqrt{2mE}$.

The energy approach, on the other hand, does not consider equi-weights, dp , as yielding probability. If one considers the equation $p_1^2 + p_2^2 = E/2m$ and takes the differential, $p_1 dp_1 + p_2 dp_2 = 0$. Noting that a given p_1 yields the value of p_2 , the probability weights are $p_1 dp_1$ and not dp_1 (with p_1 ranging from 0 to $C \sqrt{E}$). In other words, counting p vectors points in a one dimensional line with constant dp does not yield the corresponding probability given the constraint $p_1^2 + p_2^2 = 2mE$.

Momentum Sphere Surface Area

In statistical mechanics, one uses momentum phase space to count the allowable states of momentum. This is fine in summations, as argued in Part I, but does not necessarily yield the probability distribution, we argue.

The approach of (1) is to consider a gas of $n-1$ -dimensionally moving particles, i.e. each has 1 component of momentum. Then:

$$\sum_{i=1, n-1} p(i)p(i) = E/2m \quad ((1))$$

If the n th particle has $p(n)=\text{constant}$:

$$\sum_{i=1, n-1} p(i)p(i) = E/2m - e/2m \quad \text{where } e=p(n)p(n)/2m \quad ((2))$$

((2)) describes an $n-1$ sphere and (1) argues that the surface area represents the probability $P(e)$ as each point on the surface represents an allowable configuration of the $n-1$ momenta.

Ultimately, this idea leads to:

$$P(e) dp \text{ proportional to } (E-e)^{\text{power}\{ (n-3)/2 \}} \quad ((3))$$

Energy Approach of (2)

In (2), a nested energy approach is suggested. For $n=4$ particles, the 4th particle has energy e and the first particle has whatever energy is left over after particles 2 and 3 have been assigned energies. It is suggested that:

$$P(e) \text{ proportional to } \int_0^{E-e} de_2 \int_0^{E-e-e_2} de_3 \quad ((4))$$

This approach ultimately leads to:

$$P(e) \text{ proportional to } (E-e)^{\text{power } (n-2)} \quad ((4))$$

In the high n limit, the approach of (1) yields $P(e)$ proportional to $(E-e)^{\text{power } (n/2)}$ while the approach of (2) to $P(e)$ proportional to $(E-e)^{\text{power } n}$.

We try to investigate this difference by considering the $n=2$ case.

$n=2$ Particles and Probability

If one uses momentum space to count particles, then for $n=2$, particle 1 has a momentum p_1 lying on a line from 0 to $\sqrt{2mE}$. If one knows p_1 , one automatically knows p_2 . Thus, one may count p_1 values by dividing the p -line into equispaced dp values. This is fine for counting, but we argue that it does not give the probability, because it ignores effects of the constraint $p_1^2 + p_2^2 = 2mE$. This approach leads to probability \sqrt{E} associated with a p -line in keeping with the ideas of (1).

The constraint: $p_1^2 + p_2^2 = 2mE$ ((5)), however, leads to:

$$p_1 dp_1 + p_2 dp_2 = 0 \quad ((6))$$

We still argue that given p_1 , one knows p_2 , but the probability weight is not dp_1 (which is fine for counting dp), but rather:

$$\text{Probability proportional to } \int p_1 dp_1 \quad ((7))$$

Thus, one does not use equispaced dp values, but rather $p dp$ ones. This leads to:

$p/2$ or a probability proportional to E and not \sqrt{E} ((8))

We suggest that this is keeping with the ideas of (2).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that counting momentum states is not sufficient for finding probability. We use the example of $n=2$ particles with 1-dimensional momentum and total energy of E . If one knows p_1 , one automatically knows p_2 . If one were to use the notion of counting momentum states of p_1 , one might consider a line with $p=0$ to $p=\sqrt{2mE}$ with equispaced dp_1 , with each cell representing an allowable p_1 value. This leads to a probability integral $\int_0^{\sqrt{2mE}} dp_1 = \sqrt{2mE}$. This is keeping with the approach of (1), we argue..

We suggest, however, that the constraint $p_1^2 + p_2^2 = 2mE$ yields: $p_1 dp_1 + p_2 dp_2 = 0$. Given p_1 , one knows p_2 , but the probability weight is $p_1 dp_1$ and not dp_1 . We suggest that probability is proportional to integral $\int_0^{\sqrt{2mE}} p_1 dp_1$ which, in turn, is proportional to E and not \sqrt{E} . This is in keeping with the approach of (2).

References

1. . Lopez-Ruiz, R. and Calbet, Z. Why the Maxwell Distribution is the Attractive Fixed Point of the Boltzmann Equation 2006 <https://arxiv.org/pdf/nlin/0611044.pdf>
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution From a Microcanonical Power Law Part II (preprint, zenodo, 2023)